

EFFECTS OF PANEL STIFFNESS ON SLAMMING RESPONSES OF COMPOSITE HULL PANELS

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SUMMARY

Controlled water slam testing of composite hull panels was conducted to study the effect of hydroelasticity for three panels with different stiffnesses. The experimental methodology successfully characterised the hydroelastic behaviour, which included kinematic as well as inertial effects. Hydroelastic effects included changes in panel geometry, local velocity, fluid pressures, and panel structural responses.

Keywords: Marine, panel, hydroelasticity, sandwich, dynamic, slamming, experiments

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used in the structures of high performance marine vessels because of their high strength to weight ratios. The high strain limits and relatively low stiffness of these materials results in panels that can undergo significant deformations during dynamic loading events such as slamming with the water surface. Current structural dimensioning criteria for high-speed craft are typically based on treating the hydrodynamic loads as static uniformly distributed pressures, with pressure magnitudes given by empirical formulae. In reality the water pressure acting on most hull structures is neither uniformly distributed nor static, and it is affected by the response of the structure upon which it acts. The simplified modelling of this actual non-uniform, transient, dynamic, and coupled loading can restrict the ability to design an optimised structure that makes full use of the properties of the composite materials. Limitations in the prevailing methods have been discussed further by Rosén et al [1].

Slamming events typically produce a short duration, high magnitude pressure pulse followed by a lower magnitude residual pressure. This pressure distribution travels across the panel width during immersion of the panel. The pressure pulse magnitude and propagation speed are critically dependent on the impact velocity and deadrise angle of the impacting body. As the panel deforms in response to the dynamic pressure loading, the kinematic boundary conditions (i.e. geometry, velocity and acceleration conditions) at the fluid-structure boundary change. This affects the pressure distribution, which in-turn affects the panel response. This kinematic coupling between the fluid and the structure is one type of hydroelastic effect. Another type of hydroelastic effect is related to inertia, where the relationship between the loading rate and the ability of the structure to respond can have significant influence on the panel response. In practice,

the kinematic and inertia related hydroelastic effects will combine, with the significance of each depending on the details of the particular structure and loading.

Techniques for hydroelastic characterization of panel-water impact situations have been suggested by Faltinsen [2], Berezniński [3], Bogaert&Kaminski [4], and Stenius et al. [5]. In these studies the hydroelastic impact event is characterized by relationships between the loading periods and the natural periods of the structure, thereby primarily considering inertia related effects. These methods are based on theoretical models of the hydroelastic problem, with limited or no experimental validation.

In general, there is a lack of experimental work in the literature on hydroelastic effects on marine panels. Many drop tests have used rigid models to investigate the resulting pressure distributions, such as those by Chuang [6] and Wraith [7]. Drop tests using non-rigid panels include those by Hayman et al. [8] and Katsaounis&Samuelides [9]. Forced constant velocity impact tests on rigid panels include those by Tveitnes et al. [10] and Battley et al. [11], and forced constant velocity impacts on flexible panels include those by Battley et al. [12]. However, the effects of hydroelasticity are not explicitly addressed in these studies, and the impact situations studied provide a limited dynamic span in terms of loading periods in relation to first natural periods of vibration.

The experiments presented in this paper were designed to capture the full complexity of water impacts for flexible composite panels, including kinematic as well as inertia related hydroelastic effects. The experimental methodology is reviewed and typical experimental results are presented and discussed with the purpose of evaluating the ability of the experimental approach to identify and characterize hydroelastic effects. Significant findings regarding stiffness effects for composite panels subjected to slamming are also presented and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

A Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System (SSTS) was used to undertake the panel testing. This system enables testing at programme controlled velocity profiles of up to approximately 10m/s, here focusing on constant velocity impacts. The deadrise angle of the panel (β in Figure 1) can be changed from 0 to 40 degrees in 10 degree increments. The SSTS has been used for dynamic material characterisation [13], measurement of pressure distributions [11], and characterisation of panel responses [12]. A detailed description of the SSTS is given in Battley et al. [14].

Three panel specimens were tested. The first was a flexible 9.5mm thick Solid Glass-fibre (SG) laminate comprised of 3 x 3600 g/m² biaxial E glass/epoxy. The second was a medium stiffness E glass/epoxy skin and PVC Foam Core (FC) sandwich panel with 2.5mm faces of 4 x 600 g/m² quadriaxial E glass/epoxy and a 15mm Airex C70.130 core. These panels were designed to have similar stiffness to hull lay-ups used in the high speed pleasure craft industry. The third panel was designed to have a stiffness and first natural frequency high enough for it to be considered effectively rigid for the slamming velocities being considered. This was a sandwich panel with carbon-fibre/epoxy skins and a 50mm Balteck CK100 end grain Balsa Core (BC). The 3mm

thick skins comprised 5 layers of 60/40 500 g/m² biaxial cloth and 1 layer of 400 g/m² double bias cloth. All three specimens (Figure 2) were manufactured by resin infusion at High Modulus (NZ) Ltd. The panels have planar dimensions of approximately 1030mm x 600mm, with an unsupported region of 1000mm x 500mm. Edges are simply supported by the test fixture. Table 1 lists the properties of the three panels.

Figure 1 Specimen and mounting fixture

Figure 2 Solid Glass, Foam Core and Balsa Core panels

Figure 3 Pressure Transducer and Strain Gauge Layout, a=60mm, b=107.5mm.

Table 1 Panel Properties

	Solid Glass (SG)	Foam Core (FC)	Balsa Core (BC)
Material	Solid E glass/epoxy	E glass skins, Foam core	Carbon skins, Balsa core
Thickness (mm)	9.5	t _f 2.5 t _c 15	t _f 3 t _c 50
Flexural Stiffness (Nm)	1,520	6,730	274,000
Mass (kg/m ²)	18.3	10.1	31.9

(*Flexural stiffness measured for SS and FC, predicted for Rigid)

Instrumentation included dynamic pressure transducers, resistance strain gauges, displacement transducers, accelerometers and a load cell. The pressure and strain was measured in up to five locations as shown in Figure 3. Further instrumentation details can be found in Battley et al. [14]. In this work, the term “keel” is used to define the edge of the panel which reaches the water first, while “chine” is used to designate the other edge of the panel which impacts the water at the end of the slamming event.

The experiments were designed to include the full range from quasi-static to dynamic conditions for both the SG and the FC panel. This was achieved by using the dynamic hydroelastic characterization approach presented in Stenius et al [5], where the ratio between the loading period and first wet natural period for a slamming loaded panel is expressed as equation (1);

$$R = 4 \left(\frac{\mu_{np}}{\pi} \right)^2 \frac{\tan \beta}{V} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho \pi b^3}}, \quad (1)$$

where μ_{np} is a boundary condition factor (for clamped boundaries $\mu_{np} = 4.73$ and for simply supported boundaries $\mu_{np} = \pi$), β is the panel deadrise, V is incident impact

velocity, D is sectional bending stiffness, ρ is the density of water and b is the width of the panel extending from keel to chine. From basic mechanics, impact situations for which $R > 1$ can be considered as quasi-static, while dynamic effects can be expected for impact situations for which $R < 1$. The testing speeds were chosen to include velocities around $R = 1$ for the flexible panels. In the case of the very stiff balsa cored panel however, the required velocity is very high (18.70m/s) so no dynamic hydroelastic effects are expected at the testing speeds used in this study. Table 2 summarises the velocity range and expected velocity for $R = 1$ for each panel. The tests were conducted in 0.5m/s intervals for the ranges specified. A deadrise angle of 10° was used for all tests reported in this paper.

Table 2 Panel Testing Ranges

	SG Panel	FC Panel	BC Panel
Velocity @ $R=1$ [m/s]	1.28	2.85	18.70
Range Tested [m/s]	0.5-3.0	1.0-6.0	3.0-7.0

RESULTS

Measured maximum panel displacements at the centre of the panel and at the chine edge in relation to impact velocity are presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Figure 4 shows that the maximum centre displacement of the Solid Glass (SG) panel is approximately 25mm at a slamming velocity of 3.77m/s. At this velocity the stiffer Foam Core (FC) panel deforms much less, but at higher impact velocities reaches a maximum deflection of more than 25mm. In both cases these deflections are greater than the thickness of the panels. Results for the BC panel are not shown as it was almost rigid, deforming only a few mm at the centre. At the chine however, Figure 5 shows that the SG and FC panel deformations are almost identical for the two panels. This is presumably due to the lower transverse shear stiffness of the FC panel resulting in significant shear deformation at the panel chine edge. This highlights the importance of considering the effects of localised shear deformation for sandwich panels.

Figure 4 Summary of maximum centre displacements versus velocity

Figure 5 Summary of maximum displacements 50mm from chine

As a comparison to expected maximum deflections in practice, the DNV HSLC deflection criteria [15] for example specifies a maximum allowed panel deformation of 2% of the shortest panel span, corresponding to 10mm for the 500mm span of these panels. For the SG panel this criteria is reached at approximately 1.5m/s, and for the FC panel at approximately 3m/s. The purpose of this study is however to characterise the overall phenomenological behaviour, so larger deflections were included in the study.

From the time history of the panel displacements the local velocity at the panel centre can be calculated as the rig velocity (velocity of the supporting fixtures at the panel edges) minus the panel deformation velocity relative to its edges. Figure 6 summarises the resulting local panel centre velocity for each of the specimens. As expected, in the case of the very stiff BC panel the local velocity is almost the same as the rig velocity. However there are significant transient reductions in panel velocity for the flexible SG and FC panels. At a rig velocity of 3m/s for example, the SG panel has a minimum local velocity at the centre of only approximately 1.45m/s. It is clear from Figure 6 that the panel deformation effects on the local velocity starts to become significant for rig velocities above 1 m/s for the SG panel and for rig velocities above 3 m/s for the FC panel.

From the displacement measured near to the chine support it is possible to estimate the rotation of the panel edge, and hence the reduction in local deadrise angle due to the panel deformation. Figure 7 shows the resulting change in deadrise angle at the time of maximum deflection for the SG and FC panels. It is clear that the deadrise angle changes at the chine are substantial, with the minimum deadrise angle for the SG panel reaching approximately zero degrees at 3.8 m/s, while the large shear deformation of the FC panel results in deadrise angles that are negative for impact velocities above 3.4m/s. Further investigation of these significant changes in deadrise angle is an important focus of future research.

Figure 6 Panel velocity at centre vs. test rig velocity

Figure 7 Variation in Deadrise Angle at Chine for SS and FC with Respect to Impact Velocity

Figures 8 and 9 show the time history of the local panel velocity, deadrise angle and pressure at the chine for the SG and FC panels at a nominal testing velocity of 3m/s. As expected due to its proximity to the edge support, the local velocity change at the chine is smaller than at the centre. However the deadrise angle change is large, reducing to 2.94 deg for the SG panel and 2.79 deg for FC panel. The peak pressure occurs at the time of minimum deadrise angle. Figures 10 and 11 show that at the centre of the panel

the reduction in local velocity is significant, with a minimum of 1.12m/s for the SG panel and 2.19m/s for the FC panels. Deadrise angle was not measured at the centre, however due to the deformed shape of the panel the changes in the deadrise angle at the centre are not expected to be large.

Figure 8 Local velocity, deadrise and pressure at chine for SG Panel

Figure 9 Local velocity, deadrise and pressure at chine for FC Panel

Figure 10 Local panel velocity and pressure at centre for SG Panel

Figure 11 Local panel velocity and pressure at centre for FC Panel

Figure 12 compares the pressure/time history from the SG and FC flexible panels to the rigid BC panel at three pressure transducer positions. All are for 10° deadrise angle and 3m/s velocity. In Fig 12a, the pressures at the keel are similar for all three panels during the complete spray-root passage.. After the spray-root passage the FC and BC panels have similar traces, however the flexible SG panel has significant pressure oscillations.

Figure 12 Pressures for 3m/s Slamming Impacts of the Three Panels

In the case of the centre pressure, Fig 12b, there are significant differences between the pressures for each panel. The practically rigid BC panel shows the classical shaped pressure trace, with a rapid increase in pressure followed by a relatively quick reduction in pressure. The moderately flexible FC panel has a slightly lower maximum pressure, but the pressure does not reduce as quickly as for the BC panel results. The flexible SG panel has a very different centre pressure trace. This has a smaller initial peak (at 230ms) than the other panels, but then has a second higher peak followed by significant pressure oscillations about a higher residual pressure.

Fig 12c shows that the flexible SG and FC panels have higher pressures at the chine, particularly the very flexible SG specimen, which has nearly twice the maximum pressure as the BC panel. The increased pressure at the chine is believed to be caused by the reduction in local deadrise angle due to the panel deformation.

These observations for the impact event in Fig 12 are general for all impact velocities studied, and there is a clear trend of increasing peak pressures at the chine and increased residual pressure with increasing panel flexibility. This agrees well with numerical results in Stenius et al [16], and experimental comparisons between uniformly loaded and slam loaded panels in Battley et al [12]. This will lead to overall increases in load on more flexible panels. In particular there are significant increases in transverse shear force at the chine edge of more flexible panels which is critical for sandwich composites where it can cause core shear failures during slamming events.

Displacements in the centre of the SG panel and FC panel were presented in Figure 4. As expected the panel responses increase with decreasing panel stiffness for the same impact velocity. The same is seen for the laminate strains, i.e. increasing strains for decreasing stiffness. As an attempt to identify the hydroelastic inertia effects on the panel responses, the measured displacements and strains are scaled by D and D/z_{\max} respectively, where D is the panel stiffness while z_{\max} is the normal distance from the panel neutral plane to the panel surface. The scaled results are presented in Figure 13(a) for the displacement and 13(b) for the strains. According to general plate theory (e.g. Timoshenko [17]) the scaled results would be equal for the two panels if the impact situations did not include any hydroelastic effects and if shear deformations were negligible. In the previous section clear hydroelastic kinematic effects were however identified, and it was demonstrated how local variation in impact velocity and impact angle due to panel deformation resulted in increasing pressure loading with decreasing

panel stiffness for the same impact velocity. It could be expected that the observed increasing pressure loading for decreasing panel stiffness would result in a corresponding increase in panel responses. This would imply that the scaled results in Figure 13 would be larger for the more flexible SG panel than for the FC panel. However, according to Figure 13 the scaled panel responses are smaller for the more flexible SG panel. This apparent contradiction could partly be related to shear deformations in the FC panel, but the main reason is probably hydroelastic inertia effects in the more flexible SG panel. According to equation (1) and Table 2 the FC panel can be considered as quasi-static for most of the impact velocity range in Figure 13, i.e. $R > 1$ for $V < 3$ m/s. However, for the SG panel $R < 1$ when $V > 1$ m/s, and hence the deviation of the SG panel results from the FC panel results when $V > 1$ m/s can therefore be related to hydroelastic inertia effects for the SG panel. This clearly illustrates the complexity of the hydroelastic problem where kinematic effects and inertia effects are combined and interrelated. It also demonstrates the ability of the presented experimental methodology to characterise the full complexity of the hydroelastic problem.

Figure 13 Scaled displacements and laminate strains in the centre of the panels.

CONCLUSIONS

Controlled water slam testing of composite hull panels has been conducted to systematically study the effect of hydroelasticity for three panels with different stiffnesses. The experimental methodology successfully characterised the hydroelastic behaviour, which included kinematic as well as inertial effects. Significant kinematic effects were identified, including large reductions in local deadrise angle at the chine, leading to much higher peak pressures than for rigid panels. This is particularly important for sandwich panels, as this is the most critical region for transverse shear failures. Reductions in local velocity at the panel centre result in lower peak pressures at this point, however there are increased residual pressures for flexible panels. Despite the increased residual pressures, when the flexural stiffnesses of the panels are considered, the centre deflections and strains for the most flexible solid glass-fibre panel are lower than expected compared to the sandwich composite panel. This suggests that hydroelastic inertia effects do have a significant effect on the panel responses.

Further research is needed in this field to better understand the hydroelastic effects, and to develop improved analysis and design methodologies that can account for the behaviour. As part of this work, the experimental characterisation will be extended to include additional deadrise angles, alternative panel boundary conditions, and further variations in panel stiffness.

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